

REPORT 2013

STAKEHOLDER INTERACTION SURVEY

Task:	Stakeholders promotion and impact: governments and industry
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Deliverable:	Brokerage events with stakeholders at national and European level
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1. SUMMARY

This report is part of the Month 36 Deliverable 8.2, task 8.1 `Brokerage events with stakeholders at national and European level. Stakeholder promotion and impact: governments and industries`. The aim of task 8.1 is promoting EPOS to governmental and industrial stakeholders. Before promoting EPOS to stakeholders, these stakeholders must be identified. For this reason, the Stakeholder Survey was developed by EPOS management, ORFEUS and the University of Bergen (UiB). UiB conducted this questionnaire and analyses the results. The outcome, both the identification of various stakeholders as well as how the different Research Infrastructures (RIs) in EPOS are funded, can be found in this report.

2. INTRODUCTION

This WP will promote EPOS both within and outside the consortium, promote EPOS among all four categories of stakeholders: (i) National Research Organizations & funding agencies, (ii) EPOS data providers, (iii) RI data users (including Academia) (iv) data and services providers and users outside the research community (including industry). This WP will not only address the existing consortium, those that already are familiar with EPOS, commercial stakeholders (to be identified further during the project), but also new countries, academia and where possible the new generation geosciences researchers. The strategy is based on the use of the e-infrastructure of the project with the website providing information (e.g. news, deliverables, project plan and participation options) and also interaction (portal to resources, stakeholder feedback).

2.1 Task Objectives

- Providing outreach and dissemination
- Identifying further potential downstream users
- Promoting the EPOS Research Infrastructures
- Develop capacity building through specific training initiatives
- Assessment of EPOS impact on stakeholders and users

2.2 Task Participants

Task Leader: UIB, with relevant contributions from INGV, ETHZ, IMO

EPOS promoting actions addressing mainly category (i) and (iv) stakeholders, both directed towards countries within and outside the consortium. In collaboration with WP1, WP4, WP5 and WP7 this task will prepare and maintain a comprehensive list of category (i) and (iv) stakeholders and define the Providers and Users (P&U) commission. The promotion will be done in close coordination with contributions from WP1-7, data suppliers and users.

Promotion through targeted activities at EPOS annual meetings and major relevant European conferences like EGU, ESC, are among its activities.

Subscribers to this task on the EPOS intranet (collaborative area):

- Kuvvet Atakan, University of Bergen, Norway (task leader)
- Daniele Bailo, INGV, Italy
- Alessandro Bartoloni, INGV, Italy
- Daan Belgers, ORFEUS-KNMI, The Netherlands
- Louise Bjerrum, University of Bergen, Norway
- Alice Clemenceau, CNRS, France
- John Clinton, ETHZ, Switzerland
- Wojciech Debski, IGFPAS, Poland
- Torild van Eck, ORFEUS-KNMI, The Netherlands
- Russ Evans, BGS, United Kingdom
- Domenico Giardini, INGV, Italy
- Lars Ottemöller, University of Bergen, Norway
- Luca Postpischl, INGV, Italy
- Mathilde Sorensen, University of Bergen, Norway
- Kristin S. Vogfjörð, IMO, Iceland

3. IDENTIFYING CURRENT AND POTENTIAL FUTURE STAKEHOLDERS

Before promoting EPOS actions to stakeholders the relevant National Research Organizations (governmental stakeholders) and data-service providers and users outside the research community (industrial stakeholders) the different stakeholders must be identified. Each RI institution within EPOS should fill out the form concerning both current organization level and funding, as well as giving input for which funding (governmental or industrial) they could see relevant for the future.

3.1 Identifying questions

After identifying the relevant questions, and listing relevant industries (Energy, Mining, Construction, Aviation and Other) including sub-categories, the questionnaire was sketched with a flowchart to better understand the conditional answering process in the formed questionnaire. This flowchart, and a list of the questions, was uploaded to the intranet of EPOS under the discussion “Task #1: Task 8.1 Stakeholders promotion and impact: governments and industry” where participant had the opportunity to give feedback.

Based on early indication from people (not initial part of this work and task, but with potential expertise which could be valuable for developing this survey) interested in this work, the feedback on the developed questionnaire was rather disappointing. However,

feedback was received and the questionnaire (including flowchart) was updated accordingly. The process took approximately 1 month, before it was transformed into an electronic form.

The questionnaire is divided into four parts, where the first concerns identification of institution, for which RI the questionnaire is filled out, and the current status of the organization. The second part concerns governmental funding, while the third part concerns industrial funding. Finally, the last part regards confidential issues.

After the questionnaire was set up electronically more feedback, from the subscribers in the task 8.1 group on the EPOS Collaborator Area, was received and the questionnaire and flow chart was edited accordingly. The final version of the flow chart and the questionnaire are included in Appendix 1 and 2, respectively.

3.2 Technical platform used for the survey and some practical issues

There are several alternative technical solutions for electronic surveys. In this study, we have adopted the *Jotform* (www.jotform.com). In the preliminary version of the Questionnaire a *Google* form was used. However, due to limitations in the *Google* form compared to other tools (especially in the case of making long dropdown menus and long tick menus), as well as the concerns raised by the Norwegian National EPOS Consortium (NNEC) on legal implications, the electronic questionnaire was later changed into *Jotform*.

Jotform allows detailed options for conditional formatting. This implies that depending on the answers given by the user in the form, certain questions can be hidden, while others can be shown. Especially for the Stakeholder Survey, this is found very valuable.

In case the user has to leave the questionnaire and return later, *Jotform* allows the user to save the data typed in. This feature is only possible, if the survey is started with a shorter form, where an automatic generated link is created consisting of the form address and the user's e-mail address. Due to the large amount of different data needed gathered in the Stakeholder survey this was implemented.

The transformation into *Jotform* took approximately 10 days, and during this time we received considerable support from the central EPOS office with regard to access of the EPOS database, and technical help to overcome problems in setting up the form.

Jotform account

In order to gather more responses than 100 we had to buy a premium account at *Jotform*. This allows us to receive 1000 answers each month, which is needed in this survey, where we expect answers from 230-250 different RIs, and due to the saving function, therefore must expect minimum the double number in submission and also including tests and people using the saving function several times.

Downtime

15.02.2015: *Jotform* was down all day. In the afternoon we receive an e-mail with information that the domain *jotform.com* has been blocked by a US government agency. However, all the premium and pro accounts were moved to a new domain (*jorformpro.com*). Kuvvet sent out a notification to all the national contact point, their closest collaborators and the RI managers about the change in the domain name.

Problems with the saving function in Jotform

Due to the length of the questionnaire, and since some data must be collected either before and during the questionnaire and it was therefore important to build in a saving function so the user could start the questionnaire and return on a later stage.

This function has been bound up to the user's e-mail address. In other words, if a user has to fill in the questionnaire for several RIs, this will overwrite the previous typed data. It was attempted to be solved to also create the personal (automatic generated) link to the name of the RI. However, *Jotform* only lets you use one input in the link (although you can put more, this will not work). *Jotform* therefore recommended that an "unique id" was used in the automatic generated link. This also makes it more difficult for a user to "disturb" another user's questionnaire, since the automatic generated link is not easy to guess.

Furthermore, the saving in *Jotform* is disturbed when a captcha is inserted. This means that when using a saving function in *Jotform*, captchas should be avoided.

In order to be able to communicate uninterrupted with the users of the questionnaire, we created a common e-mail address (epos.wp8@gmail.com).

3.3 Strategy

The questionnaire was sent out late evening on Sunday the 5th of February. Reminders were sent out on Tuesday the 14th of February (one week after the first e-mail) and again on Thursday the 23rd of February (four days before deadline). Deadline was set to be Sunday the 26th of February, three weeks after the initial mail.

With only 53 submitted forms (out of approximately 200 declared Research Infrastructures within EPOS) on Sunday the 26th of February, the deadline was extended to Friday the 9th of March.

After the first extension of the deadline, the response rate was still low and it was decided to extend the deadline a second time. In addition, to increase the chance of achieving a higher response rate, personal emails were sent out instead sending mass emails. As the response rate remained low, the questionnaire was not closed until 17th August 2012.

The rates of submission are shown in Figure 1. There is a clear tendency that the submission activity increases as we approach the deadline (and in the following days).

Figure 1. Submission activity on the Stakeholder Survey.

4. OUTCOME OF THE STAKEHOLDERS SURVEY

After several extended deadlines the Stakeholder Survey on *Jotform* was closed on the 17th August 2012.

A total of 170 questionnaires were filled out and the results are presented below. It is important to note that at the time the Stakeholder Survey was conducted, the number of EPOS Working Groups (WGs) were restricted to 8 WGs, which was later expanded with 2 more WGs. These are therefore not included in the analyses. Also, all results are anonymous as some respondents indicated they did not wish to have the contact details of their stakeholders made known.

In the text below you will find references to the questions of the flowchart and the Stakeholder Survey (Appendix 1 and 2). Example: Q A2a, refers to question 2a, in section A of the Stakeholder Survey.

4.1 General results

Distribution of RI types within EPOS (Q A2a)

Among the 170 RI's surveyed, the largest proportion (41%), constitute the Seismological Observatories, followed by the Analytical and Experimental Labs (17%), GNSS and other geodetic data (12%) and the other geosciences data (12%) (Figure 2). Volcano Observatories (9%) and the geological and surface dynamics data (5%) constitute a smaller proportion of the total picture. Here it should be noted that there are significant differences in the size of the RI's and hence the distribution of the number of RI-categories may be misleading in this context.

Figure 2. Distribution of RI-categories within EPOS.

Organization of all EPOS RIs (Q A3a)

The overall distribution of the organizational types of all EPOS RI's show that the Universities have the majority (36%), followed by independent research organizations (25%) (Figure 3). The governmental institutions have only the 1/3 of the total with institutions directly under the ministries and independent governmental organizations having 15% each.

Figure 3. Organizational types of all EPOS RIs.

Detailed overview of organization per RI type

The distribution of organizational types for the different RI-categories show clear trends (Figure 4). In most of the Seismological Observatories (37%), the universities have the operational responsibility (Figure 4a). The rest is distributed relatively evenly (Figure 4a). The picture is different for the Volcano Observatories (Figure 4b) and the GNSS and other geodetic data (Figure 4d), where the typical organizational type is an independent research organization. In RI-category for the geological and surface dynamics data, most of the RI's are organized directly under a Ministry (45%) or as an independent governmental organization (22%) (Figure 4c). There is again a similar situation for the e-infrastructures and the virtual communities (Figure 4g) as well as the Analytical and Experimental Labs (Figure 4h), with respect to the division between the universities on one hand, and the governmental organizations on the other. Analytical and Experimental Labs have the largest proportion of Universities (69%), whereas the largest proportion of the e-infrastructures and the virtual communities are directly under a ministry (45%).

The remaining RI-categories, namely the other geosciences data (Figure 4e) and the satellite information data (Figure 4f) have rather a uniform distribution among the different organizational types. The overall complexity and variation in the organizational types have naturally a significant impact on the funding structures of the different RI's.

a) "Seismological observatories and RIs within EPOS" (70 in total)

b) "Volcano observations within EPOS" (16 in total)

c) "Geological and Surface Dynamics data" (9 in total)

d) "GNSS data and other geodetic data" (20 in total)

e) "Other geoscience data" (20 in total)

f) "Satellite information data" (3 in total)

g) "Analytical and experimental laboratories" (29 in total)

h) "E-infrastructure and virtual community" (3 in total)

■ Directly under a ministry
 ■ Independent governmental institution
 ■ Independent research organization
■ Other
 ■ Research Organization
 ■ University

Figure 4. Detailed overview of the organizational types for different RI-categories.

4.2 Current general RI funding – level of cost coverage (Q B2 & C2)

The two pie charts in Figure 5 show the distribution of governmental (Figure 5a) and industrial (Figure 5b) funding the RIs currently receive. Of the 170 RIs, 140 RIs (82%) receive governmental funding, of which 69 RIs (41%) have 80 – 100% of their cost covered by governmental funding.

The right pie chart shows the result for industrial funding, which is almost the opposite of the governmental funding. Among the 170 RIs, only 24 RIs (14%) receive funding from the industry. Out of these 24 RIs, none have major level of cost coverage by the industry. 147 RIs (86%) do not receive funding from the industry.

The charts above indicate that currently RIs mostly have their cost covered by governmental funding, and little by industrial funding (82% vs. 14%, respectively). This means, there is a significant potential, currently unexploited in collaborating with the industry involving funding the RI activities and the providing services in return.

Figure 5. Current RI funding (% level of cost coverage is shown in different color codes) for (a) Governmental funding and (b) Industrial funding.

Current funding from government per RI – detailed information

The level of cost coverage from government is quite similar for both the Seismological Observatories (Figure 6a) and the Analytical and Experimental Labs (Figure 6b). The majority of the cost (>50%) is covered either fully or partially (more than half), however, there is a significant portion of RI's which does not have any funding from government. The government funding for the GNSS and other geodetic data is distributed evenly between the different cost-coverage levels (Figure 6c). In Volcano Observatories (Figure 6d), the picture is quite different, where 81% have major coverage and the rest have minor coverage. In the e-infrastructure and virtual communities, there is only 1/3 which have partial funding from government, whereas the remaining RI's have none (Figure 6e). In the geological and surface dynamics (Figure 6f) and other geoscience data (Figure 6h) the level of coverage is around 2/3 of the total. In Satellite information data (Figure 6g), the level of coverage from government is less than 50% for almost 2/3 of the total number of RI's in this category.

a) Seismological Observatories

b) Analytical and Experimental Laboratories

c) GNSS and other Geodetic Data

d) for Volcano observations

e) E-infrastructure and virtual community

f) Geological and surface dynamics data

g) Satellite information data

h) Other geoscience data

■ Major (80-100%) ■ Partial, more than half (50-80%) ■ Partial, less than half (20-50%) ■ Minor (< 20%) ■ None

Figure 6. Current funding from government for different RI-categories.

Current funding from industry

Distributions of the current funding from the different industrial sectors are shown in Figure 7. The majority (53%) of the funding is associated with the Energy industry and is mainly from the oil and gas, nuclear, geothermal and hydrothermal industries. Contribution from the mining, construction and others are minor.

Figure 7. Current funding of the 170 RIs from various industrial sectors.

Current industrial funding per RI category

Distributions of the level of funding from the industrial sectors with respect to the four RI categories are shown in Figure 8. Seismological and geodetic RIs, as well the analytical and experimental laboratories seem to have larger levels of support when compared to the geosciences data.

Figure 8. Current industrial funding per research infrastructure (RI) category.

4.3 Potential industrial funding (Q C7)

The questionnaire had a section to identify the potential future support from various industrial sectors. Figure 9 shows the pie-diagram with the distribution of the potential future funding from the industry. Here, the energy, mining and construction industries are seen as the sectors with the largest potential (Figure 10).

Distribution between each sector

Figure 9. Potential future funding from industry.

Figure 10. Detailed distribution of potential industrial funding

While the expectation is high from the industrial sectors which traditionally support the RIs, such as the oil and gas, nuclear, geothermal and hydrothermal industries, mining, construction and aviation industries are also seen as potential contributors in the future (Figure 10).

5. CONCLUSIONS

There are several conclusions that can be drawn from the Stakeholder survey. In the following these are summarized.

- Universities and independent research institutions are the most common organizational type for the different RI's. However, there is quite a significant proportion RI-categories that are either directly under a ministry or are independent governmental institutions (Figure 3).
- There is a significant complexity in the various RI-categories with respect to the organizational type (Figure 4).
- In general, the majority of the RIs receive funding from government. There are only a few examples of industrial funding which fully covers the cost (Figure 5).
- Both the source and the level of funding are complicated with contributions from both the government and industry sectors. However, the contribution from the industrial stakeholders is far less than that of the government (Figure 5, 6 & 8).
- The main industrial support comes from the energy and mining industries (Figure 7).
- Most of the RI's see the potential of increased funding from the industry stakeholders in the future (Figure 9 & 10).

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Louise Bjerrum ended her involvement with the EPOS project as of June 2012. Her duties are handed over to Mo Yan Yuen since then. We thank Dr. Bjerrum for her contributions in conducting the stakeholder survey, as well as in the preparation of this report.

We appreciate the considerable help from Alessandro Bartoloni, Daniele Bailo, Luca Postpischl (all from INGV), and Daan Belgers provided during the preparation of the survey.

APPENDIX 2. THE ELECTRONIC STAKEHOLDER SURVEY

Introduction

The **EPOS Preparatory Phase Project** (www.epos-eu.org) (EC project number: 262229) asks your assistance to identify the current and potential EPOS stakeholders at national level both in government, but especially in industry. This questionnaire helps us to obtain a comprehensive European-scale view of the crucial, existing and potential, stakeholders in the construction of the EPOS Research Infrastructure.

The questions are divided in four parts: (A) "General information", the two main parts addressing (B) "Government Stakeholders" and (C) "Industry Stakeholders" and finally (D) "Finalizing the Questionnaire".

- The answers given in this survey will be used to further investigate possible interactions and finding ways of possible funding opportunities from the government and industry stakeholders.
- This survey also aims to identify the potential government and industry stakeholders where EPOS infrastructure may have an impact.

How should this survey be completed?

This form should be filled out for every national Research Infrastructure (RI); e.g. if your country has declared 5 national RIs, the form should be completed in its entirety 5 times, once for each RI.

- The survey is sent to each EPOS national representative, who is responsible for ensuring it is completed in its entirety for each RI.
- The national representative is tasked with ensuring the leader of each national participant and all Research Infrastructure managers, are forwarded the survey.
- The national representative should decide whether they prefer to complete the survey for all/some of the RI, or delegate the task to the RI managers.

Before starting the questionnaire, please see the [flow chart](#) and [pdf of the survey](#) for preparation of your answers. Depending on the amount of preparation time needed and stakeholders included in the RI, the survey may take 15-20 minutes to complete. Though the survey will only take 15-20 minutes to complete for every RI, some significant preparatory work may be required as reflection is needed to ensure all parts are sufficiently completed. Please take this into account.

Please notice; in case you leave the survey underway your answers will be saved. However, **it is important that you restart your browser** before you re-enter the survey and continue.

Deadline for completing this survey is Friday 3rd of August 2012.

For help on technical problems and questions regarding the content of the survey should be directed to Kuvvet Atakan and Mo Yan Yuen, University of Bergen, Norway (epos.wp8@gmail.com).

This work is prepared within the EPOS PP Project (EC project number: 262229), task 8.1 "Stakeholders promotion and impact: governments and industry", under WP 8 "Stakeholders interactions and dissemination (coordination)".

Part A: General Questions:

This part of the questionnaire concerns the institution and the type of RI for which the questionnaire is filled out. All personal contact information will be treated confidentially, unless agreed otherwise (see Part D of the questionnaire).

- A1 a) Name of institution/organization [drop down menu]
-> If other, please give the name of the institution/organization here: _____
- b) Country [drop down menu]
- c) Name of the RI [drop down menu]
-> If other, please give the name of the RI here: _____

d) Name of the EPOS RI contact person at the institution/organization **[drop down menu]**

->If other, please give the name of the EPOS RI contact person here _____

e) Are you the EPOS RI contact person?

- Yes
- No

-> What is your name? _____

-> Please fill in your e-mail address: _____@____.____

A2 a) For which type of RI is this questionnaire filled out? *(Only one can be chosen, and the questionnaire must be answered for each RI)*

- Seismological observatories and research infrastructures
- Volcano observations
- Geological and surface dynamics data
- GNSS data and other geodetic data
- Other geoscience data
- Analytical and experimental laboratories
- E-infrastructure and virtual community
- Satellite information data

b) Please comment on why this RI belong to the type selected in A2.c): *(This question is for those cases, where the RI name does not fit with RI type in A2.a). In case it is obvious from the RI name, please just fill in "..."* in this field.)

.....

A3 a) What is the current status of your RI organization?

- Directly under a ministry
- University
- Independent governmental institution
- Independent research organization
- Other _____

b) If your RI institution/organization is under a parent organization (as indicated in A3 a) please fill in: name and address, and possible contact person of this organization:

.....

Part B: Government Stakeholders:

B1 Do you currently receive funding for RI from the government?

- Directly
- Indirectly
- No

B2 What is the level of cost coverage?

- Major (80-100%)
- Partial, more than half (50-80%)
- Partial, less than half (20-50%)
- Minor (<20%)

B3 Please fill in the following contact details for ALL the national governmental institutions/organizations (e.g. research council) from which you currently receive funding:

(Name of institution/organization; Name of contact person; Level of institution/organization; Web site)

.....

B4 In case of other indirect funding in the form of services or affiliated research funded by governmental stakeholder(s), not included in B3, please describe those relations here. Add contact information if possible:

.....

B5 Please elaborate if necessary. E.g. if governmental institutions provide research funds/stations (seismological, GPS etc.)/ service products, etc.

.....

Part C: Industry Stakeholders:

C1 Do you currently receive funding for your RI from industrial partners?

- Yes
- No

C2 What is the level of cost coverage?

- Major (80-100%)
- Partial, more than half (50-80%)
- Partial, less than half (20-50%)
- Minor (<20%)

C3 Which industry sector provides the funding? (Tick as many as needed)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy, Oil and gas • Energy, Nuclear • Energy, Geothermal • Energy, Hydropower • Energy, Wind • Energy, Solar • Energy, Others _____ • Mining, Mineral • Mining, Coal • Mining, Other ore deposits • Mining, Others _____ • Construction, Dams • Construction, Bridges • Construction, Roads/highways • Construction, Critical facilities (e.g. hospitals, refinery, governmental buildings) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction, Others _____ • Aviation, Airlines • Aviation, Airplane manufactures • Aviation, Airport/airport facilities • Aviation, Others _____ • Other, Technology • Other, Defense industry • Other, Logistics and transportation • Other, Transportation authorities • Other, Reinsurance and finance • Other, Food, agriculture and fishery • Other, Tourism and services • Other, Media and communication • Other _____ |
|--|---|

C4 Please fill in the following information for each of those industries you receive funding from: (*Name of industry, Address, Contact person, Is this industry private/state owned or a combination?, What percentage (%) of the funding of the RI comes from the industry (approximately)?*)

Industry X (e.g. Energy - Oil and gas):

.....

Industry Y (e.g. Aviation - Airlines)

.....

C5 In case of other indirect funding in the form of services or affiliated research funded by industry stakeholder(s), not included in C4, please describe those relations here. Please add contact information if possible:

.....

C6 What kind of benefits (if any) can the sponsor receive in return (e.g. tax reduction, data access, intellectual property rights etc.)

.....

C7 Please identify (other) industries (currently not funding your RI) in your country relevant to your RI? (Tick as many as you feel relevant.)

- **Energy**, Oil and gas
- **Energy**, Nuclear
- **Energy**, Geothermal
- **Energy**, Hydropower
- **Energy**, Wind
- **Energy**, Solar
- **Energy**, Others _____
- **Mining**, Mineral
- **Mining**, Coal
- **Mining**, Other ore deposits
- **Mining**, Others _____
- **Construction**, Dams
- **Construction**, Bridges
- **Construction**, Roads/highways
- **Construction**, Critical facilities (e.g. hospitals, refinery, governmental buildings)
- **Construction**, Others _____
- **Aviation**, Airlines
- **Aviation**, Airplane manufactures
- **Aviation**, Airport/airport facilities
- **Aviation**, Others _____
- **Other**, Technology
- **Other**, Defense industry
- **Other**, Logistics and transportation
- **Other**, Transportation authorities
- **Other**, Reinsurance and finance
- **Other**, Food, agriculture and fishery
- **Other**, Tourism and services
- **Other**, Media and communication
- **Other** _____

C8 Please provide the following information for the identified industries:
(Name of company and company website; Possible contact person and contact information; Is this industry private/state owned or a combination?; Indicate why you think this company is relevant)

Industry X (e.g. Energy - Oil and gas)

.....

Industry Y (e.g. Aviation - Airlines)

.....

C9 Are you aware of any national/European/Global umbrella organization or union for the industries indicated relevant for your RI in C7 and C8?

- Yes
- No

C10 Please list the names of the national/European/Global umbrella organizations or unions, as well as possible contact persons within it. Also, indicate for which type of industries the organizations/union are relevant

.....

This was the last question.

Please check the answers given (using the "**Back**" button) before you submit the form. **It is not possible to go back and change answers once the form has been submitted.** Thank you!

Please fill in your e-mail address here, if you would like to receive a summary of the answers given in this survey:

____@____.____

Enter the text shown before submitting. Thank you!

XXXXXXXXXXXX _____

[**Submit Form**]

<i>Filename:</i>	StakeholderSurvey_EPOS_REPORT_task_8-1 - FINAL
<i>Upload on:</i>	23 rd October 2013
<i>Submitted and approved by:</i>	Kuvvet Atakan (UiB) & Mo Yan Yuen (UiB)

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